

Strategies to Improve Efficiency of Permit-To-Work during Shutdown: Case Study of Selected Midstream Gas Companies in Western Ghana

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Abstract

This study investigates strategies to improve the efficiency of traditional paper-based permit-to-work (tPTW) systems. The administrative dimension of the permit-to-work (PTW) system was explored to identify various gaps such as delays and errors by understanding the limitations and the various ways to improve the efficiency of the paper-based PTW of selected midstream gas companies in Western Ghana between the periods of 2023-2024. The study centered on a qualitative exploratory case study design using primary data through (Lim, 2024). Purposive sampling was used for expert opinions from employees and contractors from diverse fields of the midstream gas sector through interviews and survey (Denieffe, 2020). Data was analyzed to identify patterns and practical improvement opportunities. Findings highlight ineffectiveness in the current tPTW including delays, human error, inadequate risk assessments, and administrative gaps. Research findings from 63 key participants highlighted areas for improvement for PTW infrastructure, PTW processing, PTW system integration, human resource, non-compliance and complementary electronic PTW system through capacity building for hybrid work strategies and digital upskilling to improve the efficiency of the PTW system during shutdown maintenance periods. Ultimately, the study discovered that there is always room for improvement for the PTW system fusing Demings Plan-Do-Check-Act Model, Ishikawa fishbone model and Nadler-Tushman Congruence Model for the proposed operational framework to identify the challenges and opportunities using lessons learned for continuous improvement (Ando, 2023; Isniah, 2020). These findings provide actionable insights for oil and gas companies seeking to strengthen occupational safety during critical shutdown operations.

Keywords:

Oil and Gas, Midstream Gas Sector, Permit-To-Work, PTW, Shutdown, AI, Process Improvement, Safety Management.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The oil & gas industry is divided into three (3) main segments for its supply chain as up-stream, mid-stream and down-stream presenting different levels of hazards and risk management (Nathanael, 2024). Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) is fundamental for almost all hazardous business operations that have the potential to cause harm (Akinbode, 2022; Mousavi et al., 2019). Shutdowns maintenance periods are designed to guarantee the safe and efficient functioning of facilities and equipment, reduce downtime, increase production and overall integrity of assets that have been in use over a period of time (Kalisch, 2022). In order to reduce risks such as fatalities, injuries and damages, many companies within the oil and gas

industry have developed safe systems of work and integrated them into their policies and processes, one of which is the permit-to-work (PTW) system (Sharma, 2021). A permit-to-work system is a formal document for authorization of work and control of how persons perform tasks to mitigate work accidents taking into account the hazards and potential risks by providing advice on safe procedure through precautions, controls and collaboration of interested parties (Huda, 2023; Ameen, 2022). A thorough PTW is an administrative control under the hierarchy of controls essential to identifying and controlling hazards and its associated risks (OSHA, 2023; CDC, 2022; Ajslev et al., 2022; Jusoh, 2020). They are effective in identifying and controlling possible dangers, preventing incidents and accidents in a variety of sectors (Tamara et al., 2020; Laal et al., 2019). An increase in number of requests creates various human errors as persons processing these requests unintentionally commit blunders which usually leads to near-misses and detrimental accidents (Alonso, 2018; Seif, 2021). It is imperative that there is effective management of hazards through efficient safe systems of work such as PTW systems to mitigate risks to its lowest (Oyewole, 2024; Amm, 2021). There have been a few studies undertaken for the upstream oil and gas, construction and transport industries within geographical locations such as Europe, Asia and America (Elijah et al, 2021). New studies need to be undertaken to develop strategies on how to deal with gaps in order to improve PTW management for complex onshore operations (De Freitas, 2023). The issuance of a permit to work however does not necessarily mean that the task at hand is safe but rather the steps needed to be taken to ensure work is done in a safe manner are provided for guidance (Abbasi, 2021). There are few Acts, Legal Instrument and regulations related to OSH management and compliance, however none of these regulatory or legal documents specifically speak to requirements for PTW administration especially during shutdown maintenance periods within the oil and gas industry of Ghana (Asare, 2020). Electronic PTW enhances reliability of risk assessment since we can verify the presence of supervisors by verifying GPS (Purwoko, 2020). According to (Tsopa et al., 2022), there are five steps to create safe work environments; Analysis through assessing the task, hazard identification, Risk and Hazard reduction, regular training and Communication and Improvement through monitoring and review. The specific business problem this study sought to explore was how to improve the efficiency of the administrative and operational dimension of the PTW system for stakeholders particularly with the aspect of the gaps causing inefficiencies and lack of attention to risk assessments on the field among others. Artificial intelligence (AI) has shown impressive results in recognizing non-compliance activities and detecting hazards which may augment the PTW system by leveraging cameras and sensors strategically placed on-site to monitor people and equipment to improve the effectiveness of supervision and provide timely identification of hazards on-site (Azizi, 2024). According to Mahanta (2023), it is often no small feat to manage data in the form of paper-clip to perform analytics for information related to permit to work systems.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this case study was to understand the limitations and ways to improve the efficiency of the paper-based PTW system from experiences, perceptions, expert opinions of stakeholders such as employees and contractors during shutdown maintenance periods of selected midstream gas companies in Western Ghana. The research objectives were to identify the gaps within the paper-based PTW process, to explore and to report the possible ways to improve the efficiency of the paper-based PTW system from opinions of stakeholders during the 2023-2024 shutdown periods.

1.3 Contribution and Significance

- It recommended improvements for the tPTW system selected case study companies.
- Provide rigor to risk assessment during shutdown maintenance periods.

- Provided an operational framework to improve the PTW process continuously for the case study companies.
- Identified gaps and strategies for improvement in the paper-based PTW system of the selected midstream gas companies at the western corridor of Ghana.
- Provided insight on quantitatively measuring efficiency of the paper-based PTW system to track PTW performance for improvements to be made in the future.

2. Methods and Analysis

2.1 Data Collection

Responses from key participants in the surveys (58) and interviews (5) were collected and documented by using google forms, taking notes and using a recording device during data collection. Key participants were provided with a set of instructions and a consent form before being interviewed via telephone or face-to-face using paper-based forms and recording devices for transcription and coding. Also, virtual platforms using an online form such as google forms through e-mails and social media platforms (LinkedIn, WhatsApp) were used to distribute the questionnaire with the appropriate protocols such as brief instructions and assurance of confidentiality to retrieve responses from key participants for this study. A non-probability sampling specifically the purposive sampling method was used through interviews and surveys. Research questionnaire was conducted from key participants utilizing structured questions for the survey and semi-structured questions for the interviews through 15 open-ended questions and 5 closed-ended questions. Pretest and a Pilot test of research interview and survey questions was conducted prior to the main collection of primary data through a survey using google forms and five additional interviews from experts. The Pretest was conducted through interview, the pilot test conducted through surveys and the main data collection through expert opinions from surveys and interviews. Three case study companies were pre-selected for this study with total population of about 3000 persons including employees and contractors. Target population of about 300 persons therefore the use of the principle of saturation was expected at 30% of the target population translating to 90 persons, two-thirds represented employees and one-third represented contractors. Data saturation was achieved at about 60 key participants as no new data was collected from subsequent responses due to similarity to the responses already collected.

2.2 Data Analysis

Text excerpts were retrieved from the responses, coded by labelling them with a general phrasal idea called codes and the various codes then categorized into their related themes. Data analysis was purely coded manually using Thematic coding in an excel spreadsheet. This ensured that the information was represented appropriately without watering down relevant information as AI tools may often miss out some essential details from the empirical data collected from the key participants. Thematic coding analysis using five main steps (Prepare and Understand data, Categorize the data into Codes, Identify Themes from codes, Review Identified Themes, Interpret and Report Themes) were used to arrive at the various themes for qualitative data analysis. The thematic coding table consisted of Text Excerpts, Code Categories and Themes. Each relevant question from the research questionnaire was treated separately in different tables as the responses presented a vast amount of information to be analyzed.

3. Theoretical Background

The study was inspired by three theories that fit into the concept of improvement. These theories are Deming's Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) theory, Ishikawa Fishbone Analysis Model and Nadler-Tushman Congruence Model. According to Kao (2023), efficiency is typically a ratio of output to inputs. An efficiency model can be used to evaluate and improve the system while suggesting corrective actions for future implementation to the PTW system in addition to the use of analytics from the permit-to-work system to make informed decisions for changes

which will subsequently provide long-term benefits to the performance of the PTW system and the overall health and safety of the organisation (Gamarra, (2021).

Fig. 1 Operational framework of Proposed Permit-to-work Efficiency Model (Source: Author) The models are blended into three parts: Permit-to-work Process, Permit-to-work Performance, and Permit-to-work improvement. The PDCA model (Continual improvement) will be used to explore the various components of the Permit to work system from the planning stage to the act or improvement stage, the Ishikawa Fish bone analysis model (Root cause analysis) will be conducted to explore the factors that affect the performance of the permit-to-work process, the Nadler-Tushman (Performance Improvement) model illustrates the inputs used, strategy incorporated, transformation of the process to achieve the aim, the output performance, feedback from the performance and the measures to improve based on feedback which allow inputs to be modified. Incorporating these models allows the opportunity to explore the various concepts, how they relate to each other and how they can be analyzed using the individual models within the conceptual framework to achieve the research aim and objectives. The visual representation for the operational framework of the proposed permit-to-work efficiency model allows the research question about how factors or inputs of the permit-to-work (PTW) system can be further improved. It depicts the process to allow root cause analysis that will identify gaps/limitations and suggest alternative permit-to-work (PTW) systems and determine whether it will improve efficiency or otherwise. It will also allow for feedback from stakeholders to air their views on potential benefits on substituting the system infrastructure to a different and more efficient alternative PTW system during the shutdown period. Further studies that would use the quantitative approach could use the proposed measure of its efficiency as the ratio of the output (PTW Performance) to input (PTW Management), with this output-input ratio multiplied by 100 to gain the efficiency of the PTW system in percentage.

Fig.2 Proposed Quantitative Measurement of Permit-To-Work Efficiency (Source: Author)
 Proposed quantitative measurements for PTW management (M) is a fraction for the summation of the score of various individual parameters (p) (communication, risk assessment, documentation, etc) ranging between the values 1-100 for each value of p divided by the total number of parameters (n) representing $M = p/n$. For example, for eight (8) parameters which all have a perfect score of 100, we will have 800/8 to give a score of 100 for PTW management. Similar calculation applies to PTW performance $P = k/i$.

After gaining the score for the PTW management (Total Input (M)) and the PTW Performance (Total output (P)), an output-input ratio will be multiplied by 100 to gain PTW Efficiency (E) which will be in percentage.

Proposed PTW Efficiency (E) = (Total output (P)/ Total Input (M)) x 100 = E%

4. Key Findings

Responses from key participants will be analyzed and presented in a tabular form. There will be graphs and tables for demographics, useful charts and thematic coding respectively. The analysis tool that will be used here is thematic coding, after which the various themes for the various relevant questions will be interpreted in the subsequent chapter. Summary of Demographics saw high male participants as compared to females, dominant age group was (25-29) years, dominant education level was Master's Degree and dominant experience level was average (3-4) years.

Graph 1 Gender and Age Distribution

Graph 2 Education and Experience Distribution

Questionnaires were tailored to venture into the various opinions and perceptions surrounding the PTW system that have an impact on its efficiency. Factors for PTW management included Coordination and Communication, Risk Assessment and Controls, Training and Competences, Clarity of Roles and Responsibility, Documentation and Infrastructure while factors for PTW performance included Accident/Incident Rate, Lost Time Injury Rate (LTIR), PTW Lead-Time and Safety Culture/Compliance Rate to name a few (Ibekwe, 2022). Finally, the overall perceptions and opinions from experts on PTW management and PTW performance were explored and themes were derived from their responses. There were various themes generated using the thematic coding data analysis for the responses from the questionnaire. These themes gave a vivid depiction of the experiences, opinions and perceptions of the key participants. Some gaps were inadequate training and competences, poor coordination as PTW conditions changes, poor infrastructure to capture, visualize and apply data/lessons being collected, stressful process for job performer, difficult storage, traceability and retrieval of PTW, difficult to make-out handwriting, limited space on PTW sheet, terminologies, low understanding and appreciation of risk assessment, lack of adequate PTW authorities and centralized system, misunderstanding between stakeholders during the PTW processing, availability of key personnel, poor handling leading to misplacement and damage to PTW documents, lack of understanding of the roles, responsibilities and community resistance, inadequate controls, lack of coordination, no display of PTW and poor monitoring, inadequate risk assessment reviews and double checks for hazards and controls, non-adherence to PTW procedure, inadequate controls and low supervision, unavailable team members during JSA, create delays, miscommunication, poor accountability, inadequate real-time updates, human errors and negligence to close-out PTW, network connectivity issues and poor communication among stakeholders and job performers by-passing PTW system due to the processing time of PTW.

Question from Questionnaire	Theme
3. How would you describe your role for work activities during the shutdown period?	Supervision and Coordination
4. Would you describe the paper-based permit-to-work as an efficient form of safe system of work during the shutdown maintenance period and why?	Efficient but with issues
5. How are your work activities related to the paper-based permit-to-work (PTW) process during the shutdown maintenance period?	Coordination
6. In your opinion, describe the level of safety culture and compliance practiced regarding the paper-based PTW during the shutdown maintenance period?	Needs Improvement
7. Can you briefly tell me about a recent vivid experience related to obtaining and using the paper-based permit-to-work during a shutdown maintenance period?	PTW Process Issues
8. In your professional opinion do you believe risk assessments related to the paper-based permit-to-work are thoroughly conducted during shutdown maintenance periods and why?	Quite Thorough
9. In your experience do you believe monitoring work activities under the paper-based permit-to-work were thoroughly conducted during shutdown maintenance periods and why?	Effective
10. How would you describe the level of co-ordination and communication for paper-based permit-to-work (PTW) management during the shutdown maintenance period?	Quite Effective

11. What is your opinion on the amount of training and competency for stakeholders obtaining, using and managing the PTW system for the shutdown maintenance period?	Needs Improvement
13. Have you ever experienced or observed an incident during a shutdown maintenance period in which you believe could have been avoided if risk assessment were more thorough under the paper-based PTW system? If yes briefly describe the incident.	Fire Incident
15. In your opinion, what are some of the challenges or limitations you recognized under the paper-based PTW system during the shutdown maintenance period?	Poor PTW Administration
17. In your experience, what issue have you faced personally while obtaining, using or managing the paper-based PTW during the shutdown maintenance period?	Delays and Non-compliance
18. What alternative PTW systems can be incorporated to support and improve the efficiency of the paper-based PTW during shutdown maintenance periods?	Electronic PTW System
19. Why would it be beneficial during shutdown to substitute and/or improve the paper-based PTW system with a more efficient alternative PTW system?	Improved PTW Management and PTW Performance
20. In your experience, what strategies can be put in place to resolve issues faced considering the factors of the paper-based PTW management during shutdown maintenance periods?	Capacity Building: Technology and Human Resource

Table 1 Summary of Key Findings after Thematic Code Analysis

5. Discussion and Interpretation

Findings align with global studies highlighting PTW challenges in high-risk industries (Huda et al., 2023; Alonso et al., 2018). However, this research provides new evidence from Ghana's midstream sector, where shutdown operations amplify PTW inefficiencies. The introduction of electronic PTW systems, supported by training and supervisory oversight, could mitigate administrative bottlenecks (HSE Network, 2024). Importantly, a phased hybrid approach is recommended to balance digital adaptation with current operational realities. By implementing models such as PDCA Cycle, Nadler-Tushman Congruence Model and Ishikawa analysis companies can create feedback loops for continuous improvement thereby enhancing safety outcomes and reducing incident risks. The strategies can be incorporated in the inputs (coordination, communication, risk assessment, controls, trainings, competencies, clarity of roles and responsibilities, documentation and infrastructure) then tested in the circle during the Do stage to explore gaps using the fishbone "Ms" (Machine, Method, Man, Mother-Nature, Material, Measurement etc.) while executing the strategies during tasks by people using various organizational structures and organizational cultures (Chwat, 2023). These when well aligned according to the Nadler-Tushman improves performance through congruence. This improved performance will directly be proportional and translated to the efficiency of resources used. Findings after the performance of the PTW system has been reviewed through evaluations, analytics, audits and many others will provide opportunity to identify gaps (Do stage) and explore ideas to improve (Check stage). Finally, further improvements may be considered for implementation (Act stage) which will take us back to adding agreed strategies or selected improvements to the inputs (Plan stage) thereby becoming a continuous cycle of use for the three (3) merged theoretical models.

Improvements of factors for Permit-to-work management

1. Coordination and Communication

- Equip teams with ATEX devices: Provision of ATEX or intrinsically safe tablets/mobile devices to allow swift collaboration and communication between stakeholders during PTW planning, request, issuance, monitoring, review and closure will allow easy and immediate access to important related documents, real-time PTW updates and real-time risk assessment related to PTW system with real-time and automated notifications.
- Consistent Pre-start Meetings: Kick-off meetings and consistent stakeholder engagement through daily toolbox talk and PTW meetings with participation and commitment from top management will drastically enhance collaboration and communications channels of stakeholders during shutdown periods.
- Digitize display of PTW at facilities: Another improvement factor for the PTW system during shutdown was to incorporate a digital display in addition to the paper-based PTW in-case it is misplaced or inaccessible due to the location of the job performers. This allows a total overview as a dashboard to easily access information regarding ongoing works within the facility rather than also going to the individual job performers.
- Additional communication devices: Including more communication devices during shutdown maintenance periods will improve communication and collaboration as there will be a seamless two-way communication between work clusters for swift responses during the PTW process and especially during monitoring for work activities. For example, 2-way over the head ear muffs with in-built radios for use within work locations with excessive noise and additional intrinsically safe walkie-talkies to communicate.

2. Risk Assessment and Control Mechanism

- Integration of lessons learned in ePTW: During risk assessments the lessons learned from past incidents can be factored in prior to issuing the PTW thereby providing more rigor to the risk assessment.
- Consistent reviews of risk assessments: Under the PTW system during shutdown, there can be a team constituted to specifically handle emerging changes in high-risk jobs every morning prior to commencement of work to be able to capture any new hazards that might have been introduced while performing the task.
- Real-time risk assessments: By introducing and using ATEX or intrinsically safe devices in the form of tablets, the misconception of reduced face-face interaction with ePTW will become a myth. HSE personnel will be able to physically go to the work location with the job performer to perform a real-time risk assessment whiles completing the permit-to-work on the same tablet rather than the usual over the table risk assessments which are usually inadequate because permit issuers and job performers are occupied in completing paper-based PTW in the office instead of being at the work location to perform a risk assessment with the job performer.
- Effective supervision and monitoring: With visible and effective supervision which requires periodic updates to the condition of the work area, monitoring will be consistent and on strict terms to allow no room for incidents or negative safety cultures of non-compliance to safety protocols thereby allowing safe work place.

3. Training and Competences:

- Consistent Training for stakeholders: Various forms of training can be conducted consistently to ensure all stakeholders are adequately competent to carry out tasks under the PTW system. A few of such training can be ePTW management training, tPTW refresher training, training on PTW (both ePTW and tPTW) for contractors a day prior to commencement of tasks, technical/special training pertinent to the PTW system, certification trainings on PTW systems etc.

- Training on IT and PTW technology infrastructure: Building competence for PTW stakeholders through additional technical training such as information technology complementary to the PTW and general IT skills. This will boost the confidence and competence of stakeholders in the providing and receiving PTW.
- Awareness on PTW Policy and Standard Operating Procedure: Avoid any non-compliance to HSE and ISO standards, Legal infringements and malpractices by sensitizing stakeholders frequently prior to shutdown activities on the policies, procedures and best practices pertinent to PTW management.
- Post-shutdown workshops: In addition, after every shutdown there can be a team of experts to assess the performance of the PTW so as to encourage continual improvement of the PTW System. This will give stakeholders the opportunity to brainstorm solutions that will make the PTW more efficient in the next shutdown. During these workshops various challenges and strategies will be explored.

4. Clarity of Roles and Responsibility:

- Increase staff strength of HSE personnel: Key participants categorically mention how the number of HSE personnel are low. This creates overwhelming instances especially under the paper-based PTW system during the shutdown periods as there are numerous requests for task that are high risk in nature. This will prevent HSE persons and other PTW stakeholders from multitasking and being susceptible to human errors/negligence as there will be clarity in the role that each individual is expected to perform effectively without doubt.
- Evaluation of roles and responsibilities: The role and responsibilities handled by certain key players will also be evaluated to ensure there are putting out maximum effort and allow room for improvement. This will drive ownership and commitment to roles and responsibilities as stakeholders will gain clarity and accountability.

5. Documentation and Infrastructure

- Electronic or Paperless PTW System: Digitizing the permit-to-work system for use during shutdown maintenance periods comes with a vast number of benefits particularly by drastically reducing administrative delays and processing time during issuance of PTW when paired with the paper-based PTW system. Due to the high number of PTW requests during shutdown maintenance periods, ePTW will be able to handle large number of requests seamlessly and the paper-based PTW system will support the electronic PTW system as and when technical challenges may arise.
- Centralized software with dashboard: The ePTW platform software will allow a clear overview of PTW status and analytics for each facility and allow restricted access to job performers who are provided with the link to make a request for a PTW off-site (using a mobile device or computer) while permit issuers receive notifications of these PTW requests on-site (using ATEX devices). Software integration of the ePTW system to others such as maintenance work orders, lessons learned from incident investigations, management of change, project controls for quick access to related documents such as method statements, job performer licenses/certificates, P&ID drawings will allow automations through the software application for automated work orders, automated emails to key persons who will receive notifications and respond promptly rather having to chase these persons down physically.
- Frequent review of PTW Infrastructure: Regular audits and additional resources to improve the PTW infrastructure will drastically allow continues improvement to allow the PTW system to mature further and be more efficient especially during shutdown maintenance periods. Typical example is use of ATEX devices to receive PTW request, conduct risk assessments, amend PTWs, input digital signatures, etc.
- Introduction of AI infrastructure: Incorporation of AI assisted ePTW will allow the use of various features that will allow for prediction and swift detection of hazards, unsafe acts, unsafe conditions and non-compliance so as to assist HSE professionals to advise workers on safe

practices promptly during monitoring of work activities. These features include but are not limited to temperature sensing, poor housekeeping, missing PPE detection, missing guard detection, gas detection, spillages, collision prevention, biometric facial recognition, near-misses etc.

- Barcoding or QR codes for tracking: A summary sheet of the PTW that is issued using the ePTW system can be printed with a barcode or QR code for better tracking and access to information.
- Cloud-based storage solutions: The issued and completed PTW can be stored electronically in tiers for records and archive traceability and quick future reference. This can be done in secure solid-state drives, internal storage drives, cloud storage solutions (i.e. Dropbox, One drive, Google drive etc.)
- Inclusion of casings for paper-based PTW: In the case of expose to environmental factors and human negligence, the paper-based PTW can enclosed in a plastic document pouch to avoid it from being torn, wet area (moist working areas, rain), dirty work locations (excavation, oily areas) and windy work locations.

Improvements of factors for Permit-to-work performance

1. Low Total Recordable Incident Rate (TRIR)

- Thorough Risk assessment and control mechanisms
- Incorporating lessons learned from other companies
- Rich amount of training and competence
- AI assisted PTW and Hazard Identification
- Strict supervision and monitoring

2. Increased Positive Safety Culture and Compliance Rate

- Enhance clarity on roles and responsibilities through refreshers
- Consistent stakeholder engagement and communication
- Encourage stakeholder contribution and participation
- Reward and recognition system

3. Reduced PTW Lead-Time

- Additional Human resource capacity
- Technological infrastructure capacity
- Proper planning and timely requests
- Effective communication and coordination

6. Implications and Recommendations

The proposed operational framework can be used to improve PTW systems in addition to key findings regarding this research questions reflected responses from key participants and experts such as Frequent Training Sessions, Running a complementary tPTW and Electronic PTW, AI installations for monitoring and hazard identification, Inclusion of intrinsically safe portable devices, Automations and eSignatures, Increased number of Permit Issuers, Mobile App integration, Barcoding and QR Codes, Centralized software with dashboard, Cloud-based storage solutions, Integrated Risk management program and provision of a Protective covering for paper-based PTW. The implications to implementing the recommendations will reflect on reduction of PTW processing lead times during issuance allowing timely completion, improved retrieval and storage of PTW documentation and related documents, easier traceability, approvals, access, coordination and clear legibility, improved real-time risk assessment and reference from lessons learned in incident investigations thereby reducing accident/incident rate, flexibility to amendments during changes in work activities, addresses issue of misplacement and damage to paper-based PTW and better clarity, improved productivity, speed, convenience and handling, safety culture and compliance through participation, engagement and communication, improved coordination and collaboration with other cross

functional areas through software integration, real-time tracking of opened and closed through dashboard and analytics, platform for provision and quick review of important related document, supporting infrastructure to the paper-based system in times of high-volume request such as shutdown, quicker recognition of SIMOPS by various PTW issuers during PTW issuance, improved understanding of sections with help options to provide clarity, reduced environmental impact and human errors, reduced administrative burden associated with data entry and retrieval, notifications and record keeping efficiency.

7. Conclusions of the study

The gaps within the paper-based PTW process from experiences and perceptions were adequately identified and explored from key finding that were recognized from responses of key participants who participated in the surveys and interviews. Also, the study was able to explore and report ways to improve the efficiency of the paper-based PTW system from opinions by stakeholders during the shutdown period. The key findings of this study depict that there is generally always room for improvement within the PTW system hence making the proposed operational framework feasible for professional and academic use. Furthermore, the PTW management/process plays a huge role when factors such as coordination, communication, risk assessment, controls, trainings, competencies, clarity of roles and responsibilities, documentation and infrastructure are enhanced to allow positive outcomes of the PTW performance such as low total recordable incident rate (TRIR), increased positive safety culture and compliance rate, reduced PTW Lead-Time and improved evaluations. This will increase the possibility of further improving the PTW efficiency as the PTW system during shutdown maintenance periods will be improved (Gamarra, (2021). The recommendations from this study may therefore increase the chances of further improving the paper-based PTW systems of the selected midstream gas companies within the western corridor of Ghana and will better the PTW system when properly implemented.

This study contributes to the understanding of PTW efficiency in midstream gas companies during shutdowns in Ghana. It demonstrates that combining electronic tools with existing paper-based systems, while prioritizing training and stakeholder engagement, can substantially improve efficiency and safety. Future research should explore quantitative measurement frameworks to track PTW performance and the integration of artificial intelligence for real-time monitoring.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Lawrence Schandorf: Writing - review & editing, Writing - original draft, Visualization, Software, Resources, Methodology, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization, Formal analysis. **Girish Bagale:** Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Validation. **Ransford Gyambrah:** Writing - review & editing, Conceptualization, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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